

THE IMPACT OF FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT STRATEGY ON INCREASING STUDENT MOTIVATION IN ENGLISH CLASSES

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Abstract. The main goal of this article is to introduce various forms of formative assessment, and through data collection and interpretation, to draw certain conclusions about their impact on increasing students' motivation in learning a foreign language and to draw conclusions that will help in determining further didactic and methodological strategies in English lessons. Formative assessment helps to obtain information about the degree to which each student has mastered the educational material, and promptly identifies shortcomings and gaps in students' knowledge.

Key words: *formative assessment, research methods, survey, observation, motivation, assessment techniques.*

Our focus is on strategies for assessing learning and assessing for learning. In modern methods of teaching foreign languages and in pedagogical practice itself, teachers are often faced with the problem of assessing students in English lessons. In the educational process, special difficulties arise in assessing student learning activities, where there is a need to solve not only the problem of assessment as an indicator of the student's achievement of certain results, but also assessment as a factor in stimulating further student learning. The main goal of this article is to introduce various forms of formative assessment, and through data collection and interpretation, to draw certain conclusions about their impact on increasing students' motivation in learning a foreign language and to draw conclusions that will help in determining further didactic and methodological strategies in English lessons.

To effectively collect data, it is possible to use research methods such as:

- survey
- video interview
- monitoring the activities of students in the classroom;
- conversation with students;
- professional conversation;
- collection and processing of student work

In English lessons, it is necessary to introduce new methods of assessing students and observe what effect they will have on the educational process, how

students will react to the new assessment system, this is what formatted assessment is focused on.

During my research, a lot of photo and video materials were collected and processed. We collected and processed student work - posters, essays, self-assessment and peer-assessment questionnaires. Rich illustrative material became the basis for conclusions.

At the end of the lesson, we used the method of visual reflection, which allows us to obtain data about the atmosphere of the class and the mood of the students. This served as a significant help in preparing for the next lesson. Reflection data after a lesson using new technologies.

In the process of our observations, we came to the conclusion that several factors reduce the internal motivation of students:

- a. The teacher's stinginess in encouraging the student's performance;
- b. Unfriendly tone;
- c. Strict assessment and control by the teacher;
- d. Limited time limit.

As a result of practice, it can be noted that the new assessment criteria aroused great interest among students. It was possible to observe an increase in motivation both among students with an average level of development and among students who achieved high levels. This is due to the fact that the criteria-based assessment system is transparent, objective and accessible. Positive aspects include reduced anxiety in the classroom, the possibility of self-assessment, introspection and control. New methods introduced into the learning process caused a great resonance and positive response among students and fellow teachers. This strengthened the confidence that the chosen strategy was promising and correct. It shows students where they should put their efforts in order to achieve better results, detects and shows weaknesses in learning. In addition, criterion-based assessment is a guide to action for teachers, a tool that allows them to skillfully improve their teaching practice.

Features of formative assessment techniques include the use of analytical tools and techniques to measure the level of learning and progress of students in the process of cognition. The results of such assessments can be used to make recommendations for improving teaching and learning.

Formative assessment techniques can be divided into several conventional groups or types.

- Index card for generalization or for questions - The teacher periodically distributes cards to students with tasks indicated on both sides: Side 1: List the

main ideas from the material covered (section, topic) and summarize them. Side 2: Determine what you have not yet understood from the material covered (section, topic), and formulate your questions.

- Hand Signals - The teacher asks students to make signals indicating understanding or misunderstanding of the material (as the teacher explains a concept, principle, process, etc.). You should first agree with students about the use of these signals:

I understand and can explain (thumb pointing up)

I still don't understand (thumb pointing to the side)

I'm not entirely sure about (wave hand)

After looking at the signals, the teacher interviews the students in each group. Based on the results of the answers received, the teacher makes a decision on re-studying, consolidating the topic, or continuing to study the material according to the program.

- Traffic light. Each student has cards of three traffic light colors. The teacher asks students to use cards to show signals indicating their understanding or misunderstanding of the material, then he asks students to answer the questions: green cards (everyone understood): What did you understand? yellow or red cards: What do you not understand?

Based on the results of the answers received, the teacher makes a decision on re-studying, consolidating the topic, or continuing to study the material according to the program.

- One-minute essay. The one-minute essay is a technique used by the teacher to provide feedback to students on what they have learned about a topic. To write a one-minute essay, the teacher can ask the following questions: What is the most important thing you learned today?, What questions remained unclear to you?

- Speech samples (hints.) The teacher periodically gives students speech samples (expressions, clues) to help construct an answer.

- Three-minute pause. The teacher provides students with a three-minute pause, which gives students the opportunity to think about concepts, lesson ideas, connect with previous material, knowledge and experience, and clarify unclear points.

- Temperature measurement. This method is used to determine how well students complete a task. To do this, the students' activities stop and the teacher asks the question: "What are we doing?" By answering this question, students

provide information about their level of understanding of the task or the process of completing it.

- Mini-test. Mini-tests are designed to assess the actual knowledge, skills and abilities of students, i.e. knowledge of specific information, specific material.

- Elective (selective) test. The teacher distributes cards with the letters “A, B, C, D” to each student and asks the students to answer simultaneously, i.e. pick up the card with the correct answer. The teacher must ask students to think for 20 seconds and only then provide an answer.

- Formative test. The teacher randomly divides students into small groups (4-5 students per group). Each student receives a test question sheet and an answer sheet. Students are given time to discuss test questions in small groups. After the discussion, students complete the answer sheet on their own. Each student's scores are calculated separately.

- Self-esteem diaries/journals. Self-assessment diaries/magazines are created so that the teacher and student can evaluate the knowledge, skills and competencies acquired during the lesson, as well as the way in which this knowledge, skills and abilities were acquired, and their volume. The diaries enable the teacher to get an idea of the student's level of progress and take appropriate steps to improve the educational process.

- Formative inquiry. This is a form of assessment that immediately follows the presentation of material or any activity in the lesson. The teacher asks additional clarifying questions: “Why? How? How?...”.

- An exercise to test the assimilation of new material. The teacher creates a table of four windows (squares) with the inscriptions: “Predict”, “Explain”, “Summarize” and “Evaluate”. After explaining new material, he asks students to choose a specific square. At the same time, the teacher explains that in this way each student chooses the type of task that he will need to complete on the topic being studied. Then, depending on the choice of square, the teacher asks a question.

- Summary in one sentence. Ask students to summarize the topic they have learned in one sentence that answers the questions “who?” What? Where? When? Why? And How?”.

- Summary in one word. The teacher gives the students the task: “Choose (select) the word that most accurately summarizes the topic.”

- Written comments (written feedback). A mandatory element of assessment is providing feedback. When checking students' written work, the teacher makes his comments in accordance with the assessment criteria and the

level of achievement of the result. Comments should be clear and educational in nature.

- Verbal assessment (verbal feedback). The most common type of assessment. The teacher praised the student for doing the exercise well and thus provided verbal feedback, so the student can understand that he has successfully mastered the material or information. The teacher pointed out to the student errors in performing the exercise. He did not give any mark for the work, but he appreciated it. As a result, the student can judge what he needs to do to achieve better results.

- Self-assessment. The process by which students collect information about their learning, analyze it, and draw conclusions about their progress. A prerequisite for self-assessment is the presence of work evaluation criteria, which students should be familiar with at the beginning of studying the topic and before starting work.

- Two stars and a wish (mutual assessment). It is used when assessing students' creative works, compositions, and essays. The teacher offers to check the work of a classmate. When students comment on each other's work, they do not evaluate the work, but identify and point out two positive points - "two stars" - and one point that deserves improvement - "wish".

So, formative assessment helps to obtain information about the degree to which each student has mastered the educational material, and promptly identifies shortcomings and gaps in students' knowledge. Formative assessment allows you to qualitatively assess a student's educational achievements. It is conducted continuously and systematically, and reflects real and meaningful learning experiences that are documented through observations, case studies, analyses, samples of actual student work, interviews, portfolios, assignments, and other means.

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